

Prediction of Thermodynamic Behaviours of Aqueous Electrolytes at all Temperatures[†]

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Based upon structurally modified continuum theory, two simple approaches have been described for theoretical prediction of the free energy, entropy and heat capacity of hydration of ions and electrolytes at all temperatures. The treatments are consistent with the assumptions that the effective size of an ion in water does not change with temperature and that the Born relationship and its various derivations accurately describe the electrical part of the hydration thermodynamic functions

In the first approach, the ionic radii of an electrolyte are fixed by the experimental hydration energies at 25°. Consequently we are able to calculate the entropy of hydration over a wide interval of temperature with only one arbitrary structural entropy parameter. This structural parameter can then be used with the continuum relationships to predict the change of the free energy of hydration with temperature to a high degree of accuracy. Even the prediction of the heat capacity of hydration, which is given directly from the second derivative of the Born equation, is accurate for electrolytes at higher temperatures.

In the second approach, even the single arbitrary parameter used in the first approach has been done away with. Here one sees the solution process of a gaseous solute ion as the combination of the two steps: (i) the formation of a cavity of a suitable size in the solvent to accommodate the solute ion and (ii) the introduction into the cavity of the solute ion which interacts with the solvent. In this approach, the thermodynamic functions associated with the cavity formation have been calculated using the scaled particle theory and it has been assumed that the specific interaction free energy occurring in the near vicinity of the ion in solution, which the traditional Born equation can not recognise, is sufficiently strong and relatively temperature insensitive. As in the earlier approach, the thermodynamic prediction through this simple approach is highly accurate for free energy, entropy as well as heat capacity at a wide range of temperature.

ACCURATE prediction of some fundamental thermodynamic properties of electrolytes in solution from purely theoretical consideration has been for long one of the most important objectives of the various theories of electrolytes. In the past, many have tried to reach this goal through various means. It has now become gradually understandable that the thermodynamic and other behaviours of electrolytes in solution can best be visualised perhaps with the help of various models based on which different properties can be theoretically calculated and compared with the corresponding experimental values. Consequently, different kinds of electrolyte solution models have been proposed from time to time. A number of excellent reviews¹⁻⁵ did discuss about these models quite extensively and the same need not be repeated here. Since in the present work some unified theory consistent with many of these classical concepts would be proposed, it seems worthwhile to recall the essence of some of these traditional models as well as the present state of the problem.

Classical approaches :

Born continuum model : When the solvent medium is considered as a structureless continuous

dielectric, the free energy of solvation may be regarded as equivalent to the difference in the electrostatic energy of a gaseous ion and that of an ion in the medium of dielectric constant D . In order to evaluate this quantity, one may use the Born model⁶ where the ions are represented as charged incompressible hard spheres and the solvent as a fluid with dielectric constant D which is uniform even in presence of ionic fields. The free energy increase accompanying the charging of a single gaseous ion, *i.e.* in a medium of dielectric constant unity is $(Ze)^2/2r$ where Ze is the charge earned by the ion and r is its effective radius. If the same ion is charged in a medium of dielectric constant D , the free energy change is $(Ze)^2/2Dr$, and so the increase of free energy accompanying the transfer of the gaseous ion to the particular medium which may be equated to the free energy of solvation is given by the Born equation,

$$\Delta G_s^\circ = W_{M^+} = [(Ze)^2/2r] \left[\frac{1}{D} - 1 \right] \quad (1)$$

Modifications of the Born model : Although one can agree with the conclusion of Wu and Friedman⁷ that a change in the size of the ion on solvation does not invalidate the Born equation, the

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problem of choosing the correct solution radius of the solute ion remains to be solved. One conclusion is, however, quite certain that equation (1) gives too high negative value for the free energy of hydration (ΔG_h^0) when applied to salts (*i.e.* the neutral ensemble of the cations and the anions) and when r is taken as the crystallographic radius of the ion. Attempts have, therefore, been made to use a larger value of r for the ion in solution in the Born equation to bring down the calculated value of ΔG_h^0 to the experimental value.

Another weak point of the original Born equation is the assumption that the dielectric constant of the solvent to be constant in the neighbourhood of the ion. The treatment has been modified by Webb⁸ who allowed the variation of the dielectric constant and also for the work required to compress the solvent in the vicinity of the ion; further, by expressing the effective ionic radius as a function of the partial molal volume of the ion, it was possible to derive values of free energy of hydration without making any other assumptions concerning the effective ionic radius.

Debye and Pauling⁹ modified the Born equation and suggested

$$\Delta G_h^0 = 1/2 (Ze)^2 \left[\frac{1}{D} \left\{ \frac{1}{(r+\delta)} \right\} + \frac{1}{D'} \left\{ \frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{(r+\delta)} \right\} - \frac{1}{r} \right] \quad (2)$$

where, the first term in brackets comes from the field free energy in solution outside of the $(r+\delta)$ sphere, δ being the increment of the radius, the second term $(1/D')$ comes from the field free energy in solution in the annular space between r and $(r+\delta)$, and the last term comes from the field free energy about the ion in vacuum. If D' is taken as 1, equation (2) reduces to the Born equation with r replaced by $(r+\delta)$,

$$\Delta G_h^0 = [(Ze)^2/2(r+\delta)] \left[\frac{1}{D} - 1 \right] \quad (3)$$

The use of radius $(r+\delta)$ in the Born equation, however, corresponds to a physical model in which the charged sphere representing the ion has a different size in the vacuum and in solution.

Refinement of the Born model: The Born original model is so simple and the results obtained with it so promising that there have been a great many efforts to refine it. It has often been suggested that either the Born model or the Debye-Pauling model can at best form a basis for calculating the 'electrostatic' part of the ionic solvation energy and that this must be added to another contribution such as one would have for the discharged ion (*i.e.* a neutral species of same size)¹⁰⁻¹⁸. That is, the ionic solvation free energy is given by an equation,

$$\Delta G_h^0 = \Delta G_{el}^0 + \Delta G_{non\ el}^0 \quad (4)$$

where, the first term of the right is the electrostatic contribution and the second is the non-electrostatic contribution, which may be estimated, for example,

on the basis of the solvation energy of an uncharged species that is isoelectronic with the ion (and isostructural as well if ion is polyatomic).

Many other attempts of the refinement of the above models have been reviewed elsewhere² and it been considered that it is hard to improve on the Born model for estimating the part of solvation energetics that is particular to ionic solute. It has also been concluded that the most that one can probably learn from a theory of ion solvation based on electrostatic models in which the molecular properties of the solvent do not appear is that the thermodynamic coefficients of ion solvation can be related to those of the corresponding uncharged species.

Structural model of Frank and Wen: On the basis of wide variety of evidences, Frank and Wen¹⁴ have proposed that surrounding a solute molecule there are three regions that can be fairly well distinguished from each other. Close to the solute molecule there is an increase in solvent structure. The nature of the structure enhancement seems to be different for polar and non-polar solutes. For highly polar solutes, such as ions, it seems probable that ice-like structure is formed, lying outside this is a region where the solvent suffers disordering as a result of the opposing effects of the ion and of the surrounding water molecules. The third region comprises the essentially unperturbed water molecules. Although these concepts provide great insight into the nature of solvation and allow important qualitative predictions to be made, it is difficult to use them as a basis for quantitative calculations. These have usually been carried out on the basis of a simpler model in which only two zones are considered. The inner one generally consists of a single of water molecules, and calculations are made of the interactions between the ion and these molecules. The outer zone consists of the remaining water molecules; the interactions here are much smaller and are usually treated on the basis of a continuous model.

Molecular models: It has often been thought that a more promising approach to the theories of solvation is from a molecular model point of view. Since the pioneering work of Bernal and Fowler¹⁵ many such theories have been proposed mainly in relation to the prediction of heat of hydration of ions. Several contributions have been suggested¹: (i) formation of a cavity in the solvent, (ii) strong interaction between the ion and the solvent molecules of the first (and sometimes second) coordination shell, (iii) interactions between the solvent molecules in the coordination shell, (iv) weaker interactions between the hydration complex and the rest of the solvent molecules, and (v) further changes in the structure of water. Of course, none of these interactions is simple to calculate, especially in view of the uncertainty in the true ionic radii, in the coordination number of the ions and in the orientation of the water molecules in the coordination shell. Because of

the continuous exchange with the rest of the solvent, the water molecules in the coordination shell do not form a stable cavity with the ion, and it is only on a time average that a structure may be attributed to the hydration complex.

Most of the molecular theories consider the solvent water molecule as a sphere containing a certain number of point charges or as suggested by Buckingham¹⁶ characterised by its radius, dielectric constant, polarisability, and dipole and quadrupole moments. Apparently, to avoid the ambiguity of the Born model regarding the discrete structure of the solvent and to account for the variations in the interactions of dissolved ions and the solvent using the point charge, dipole model was suggested.

Hamiltonian models: Many of the solvation models considered above comprised one particle, representing the ion, immersed in a medium representing the solvent. In a more detailed model one may represent the medium itself by an assembly of a large number of identical particles representing the solvent molecules. As soon as this is done the methods of classical electrostatics employed in earlier models become inadequate for calculating the properties of the model system, and one must use the method of statistical mechanics.

To proceed, one needs to know, for a classical system, the Hamiltonian function for the assembly of one ion with N solvent particles,

$$H_{N+1}(P_1, \dots, P_{N+1}, r_1, \dots, r_{N+1}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} (P_i^2/m_i) + U_{N+1}(r_1, \dots, r_{N+1}) \quad (5)$$

for each set of moments, P_1, P_2, \dots and locations r_1, r_2, \dots of the $(N+1)$ particle system. In equation (5), U_{N+1} is the potential of the interaction of the $(N+1)$ particles in the specific configuration. If the particles representing the ion or the solvent molecules are not spherical, then each r_i must specify the orientation as well as the location of the particle. If angular moments are important, then each P_i must specify the angular momentum as well as the translational momentum, and the kinetic energy term in equation (5) must be written to include the contributions from angular moments. Finally, if quantum mechanical effects are to be accounted for, one employs the standard transcription to convert the Hamiltonian function H_{N+1} to the appropriate Hamiltonian operator^{17,18}.

A basic theorem in statistical mechanics is that the Helmholtz free energy $A(N+1, V, T)$ of the system of $(N+1)$ particles in volume V at temperature T is given by

$$\exp[-\beta A(N+1, V, T)] = \int dp_1 \int dp_2 \dots \int dr_1 \int dr_{N+1} \times \exp[-\beta H_{N+1}(p_1, \dots, r_{N+1})] \quad (6)$$

where, $\beta = 1/kT$ and, of course, ΔA for a solvation process may be obtained by forming the ratio of equation (6) applied to the initial and final states

of the process. Again, there is a well known transcription of equation (6) for use in cases in which quantum mechanical effects are included¹⁹.

In such a model, it is easy enough to use the mass m_i (and when appropriate, the moment of inertia I_i) corresponding exactly to that of the real ion or solvent molecule, but the potential energy function U_{N+1} is generally not well known, and in order to use equation (6), one needs to make some assumption about its form. This way of proceeding, in which one assumes a definite functional form for the Hamiltonian and then proceeds to a more or less exact evaluation of the integral in equation (6), may be called the study of Hamiltonian models.

Enormous progress has been made in recent years in the development of approximate but accurate methods of evaluating the integral in equation (6), whether directly through the use of the other exact relations. However, these methods are applicable only to models in which the potential function is pair-wise additive,

$$U_{N+1} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} \sum_{j=1}^{N+1} u_{ij}(r_i, r_j) \quad (7)$$

and are practical especially in the case that the pair potential u_{ij} depends only on the distance between the particles i and j . Of course, a model subject to both of these conditions cannot represent a hydration system very realistically. In the real system, there are not only orientation dependent forces involving charge-dipole, dipole-dipole, and higher order multipole interactions, but the molecular polarisability make U_{N+1} not pairwise additive. Of course, for a still more detailed model in which the particles are the ion nucleus, the nuclei of the N -solvent molecules, and all of the electrons, the Hamiltonian will indeed have a potential function that is pairwise additive, but the possibility of accurate evaluation of the thermodynamic properties of such a model is remote.

Recent trends :

Hybrid models: Prompted by the failures of many of the above models to represent the various aspects of the ion-solvent phenomenon on one account or other, proposals have also been put forward which combine more than one of the above concepts for solving some particular parts of the problem by one model and some other by a different model. In some of such hybrid models, the interaction of an ion and its first nearest neighbour solvent molecules (primary solvation sheath) is calculated in terms of inter-molecular forces, just as for a Hamiltonian model, while the interaction of this complex with the remaining solvent is calculated as in the theory of the Born model, perhaps the allowance for this non-electrostatic part of the solvation of the complex. There have been many studies of models of this sort² which illustrate what effects they may include. There are, however,

important problems with calculations of this type which need to be overcome before they can provide a reliable interpretation of hydration phenomenon more detailed than that from Debye-Pauling model.

In one of these above approaches, Muirhead-Could and Laidler²⁰ represented the solvent water molecule by a particle having charges at the locations of the atoms in an actual water molecule and chosen so that the model particle will have the same dipole moment as an isolated real water molecule. They assume that the complex formed by the solute ion and the solvent molecules is symmetrically constructed, with the distance from the centre of the ion to the centre of each oxygen atom of the coordinated water molecules given by the sum of the crystal radius of the ion and that of the water molecule.

The two layer hydration model of Bockris and Saluja²¹ which may be considered as a statistical thermodynamic model with a difference of degree, stresses the need for the distinction between the coordination number (*i.e.* time average number of water molecules in the first hydration shell) and the solvation number (*i.e.* the solvent molecules which move with the ion during its migration jump in the solution) for an individual ion in solution. They attempted to obtain these numbers from experimental data involving spectroscopy, compressibility and ionic vibration potential²². Bockris and Saluja²¹ also proposed that there would be two types of coordination water molecules, solvational and non-solvational, in the first layer would be consisting of partially liberated (from the characteristic hydrogen bonded structure) water molecules. There had been however some reservations²³ about the significance of the hydration numbers evaluated from ionic vibration potential together with the compressibility data.

In the hydration model suggested by Goldman and Bates²⁴ for theoretical calculation of the standard state thermodynamic functions associated with the transfer of ions from gas to water also, two different regions around the dissolved ion are treated differently in calculating their respective contributions to the solvation energy of the ion. In the first hydration region in the near vicinity of the ion where the water molecules are assumed to be discrete, an off-centred dipole is used to allow the possibility that the positive and negative ions of the same size and valency be unequally hydrated. A Born continuum treatment is subsequently used to calculate the secondary hydration effects. In this approach the values of the model parameters are obtained by fitting the model to experimental gas phase single ion hydration data^{25,26}.

Some other examples of hybrid model did consider a limited number of solvent molecules in the theoretical calculations. In these cases, the system of the solute and a small number of solvent molecules are treated as a 'supermolecule'. Such approaches have been used extensively by Pullman and Pullman and their coworkers²⁷. Recently,

related studies have been reported by Jorgensen²⁸. Combinations of supermolecule and continuum approaches have been reported by Newton²⁹, Kollman and Kuntz³⁰ and also by Schnuelle and Beveridge^{31,32}. Their statistical thermodynamic supermolecule continuum model for theoretical treatment of solvation energy and solvation effects on molecular structure and properties involve the calculation of partition function for a dissolved molecule and its first solvation shell³². The thermodynamic properties of the system follow from the partition function in the usual manner³³. The general expression for the partition function (Z_i), representative of the systems, involves E_i^{eff} the energy of supermolecular assembly of solvent (particle 1) and vicinal solvent molecules (particles 2-M) imbedded in polarisable dielectric in the integral. Maintaining a statistical thermodynamic super-molecule continuum calculation within computationally tractable limits requires special considerations of the evaluation of the configurational energy, E_i^{eff} , and the evaluation of the integrals over configurational coordinates of solvent molecules (configurational averaging). The most accurate but lengthy computational method of quantum mechanics can be avoided by several approximations, *viz.* shell method, cell method and site method. In the shell method, the range of configurational integration is restricted to the first solvation shell. The cell method involves restricting the configurational freedom of solvent molecules to mutually exclusive region of the configurational space of the first solvation shell. The site method involves assuming particular sites in the first solvation shell for solvent molecules, disposing the solvent molecules with their centre of gravity coincident with these sites, and carrying out a configurational averaging over orientational conditions.

A convenient approach to accurate energy evaluation is available from the large basis set *ab initio* molecular orbital study of ion-water and water-water interactions by Popkie *et al.*^{34,35}. The results for ion hydration obtained by Schnuelle and Beveridge^{31,32} suggests a relatively small contribution from configurational averaging. This may indicate that the configurational averaging of water in the vicinity of highly ionic sites on a dissolved molecule will in absence of other intra-molecular perturbation, such as steric effects, also contribute little to free energy of the system. An attempt to simplify the super-molecule approach by treating the solvent molecules as fixed point charges on atomic centres was reported by Noell and Morokuma³⁶. However, this point charges model at the present stage is not useful for practical calculations since it keeps the solvent molecules in arbitrarily fixed positions.

Among other recent approaches to study ion-solvent interactions Claverie *et al.*³⁷ considered these different models: (i) a discrete model, according to which a finite number of solvent molecules are placed around the solute molecule and the total interactions energy is calculated by simplified formulas, (ii) a continuum model, according to which the solvent surrounding the solute

is simulated by a continuum medium (the method of calculation takes into account the actual shape and charge distribution of the solute molecule), and (iii) a discrete-continuum combined model, according to which a small number of solvent molecules (corresponding to so called solvation sites) interacting strongly with the solute are treated as discrete, while the remaining solvent is simulated by a continuous medium. Apparently, the discrete model gives a representation of the 'structure' of the solvent molecules around the solute and provides satisfactorily the primary solvation sites. The continuum model gives the solvation energy with good accuracy, and the combination of discrete and continuum model should be especially appropriate for studying ionic molecules.

Chan *et al.*⁸⁸ considered a model electrolyte solution comprised of a mixture of ions of equal size, modeled as hard spheres plus embedded point charges, in a dipolar solvent, modeled as hard sphere (of different size to these of the ions) plus embedded point dipoles. The statistical mechanics of this model was treated in the mean spherical approximation (MSA) which is natural extension of the Debye-Hückel theory of electrolytes to include discrete charges and dipoles of finite size. The authors have been able to recover a familiar empirical correction to the Born energy, indicate the pitfalls in assuming empirical functional forms to describe dielectric saturation and to demonstrate derivations from the continuum description of ion-ion interaction at close separations where because of the discrete nature of the solvent, the solvent molecules can no longer screen Coulomb potential property. However, due to this inherent inability to handle the non-linearities, the fluctuation potential and image effects the MSA cannot be relied upon to give accurate quantitative description of ion dipole systems.

Warshell⁸⁹ recently presented a new model referred to as the 'surface constrained soft sphere dipoles' (SCSSD) model in order to overcome some of the problems in the theoretical treatment of solvent effect. On one hand, it avoids the problems of dielectric continuum approaches by explicitly including solvent molecules. On the other hand, it overcomes the extreme inefficiency of the super-molecule approaches by drastically simplifying the solvent molecules while retaining their main physical features. This is done by representing the solvent molecules as soft sphere point dipoles and minimizing the solute-solvent energy with respect to the orientations and positions of these dipoles while constraining the surface dipoles to have positions of the bulk molecules. This model, however, like any other dipole model cannot reproduce the hydrogen bond network of aqueous solutions, though by adjusting the density and dipole length it is possible to constrain the dipole model to reproduce the solvation energies observed in aqueous solutions.

Recently, some forceful attempts have been made to obtain a structural view of liquid water

and aqueous solutions by the application of various simulation techniques and consequently to evaluate ion-hydration phenomenon⁴⁰. Either for Monte Carlo or molecular dynamics simulations which belongs to the above process a representation of water-solute interaction potential is required, and if the solute molecules are to be allowed to move in the molecular dynamics calculation the solute-solute potential is also needed. The thermodynamic production through above process no doubt needs lengthy computer calculations⁴⁰.

In spite of all those efforts it is apparent that the important goal of the theory of electrolytes to predict some fundamental thermodynamic property of ions in solution from first principles is still far enough. The two stumbling blocks to use continuum model, *viz.* (i) obtaining or even defining the ionic radius to the required degree of accuracy, and (ii) lack of detailed knowledge of the dielectric constant in the vicinity of an ion are yet to be removed. The molecular approaches as well as the hybrid models are also most of the time complicated and success is very limited in certain specific cases with adjustable parameters. A number of features of the electrolyte behaviour have, however, been qualitatively correlated with a more structurally based model, such as Frank-Wen proposal¹⁴, but the attractive features of the approaches have not yet been translated into a quantitative theory. The quantum mechanical approach considering the proper Hamiltonian and also various simulation methods are quite complicated and need elaborate computations.

We have however found that the continuum theory is capable of an accurate description of the thermodynamic properties of electrolytes when allowance is made for proper standard states and structural properties of ion-solvent interactions. The present paper describes two different approaches based upon structurally modified continuum theory which can be used to calculate the thermodynamic behaviour of electrolytes. In the first approach, we shall consider a structural entropy parameter along with the Born entropy term to represent the entropy of hydration. In the second approach, even this single arbitrary parameter will be eliminated. A temperature insensitive specific ion-solvent interaction free energy term will be introduced in addition to the Born free energy to represent the total free energy of interactions. Comparisons between the theoretically predicted thermodynamic quantities with those obtained directly from experiments will be provided in both the cases.

Definitions :

Dissolution of gaseous ions (electrolytes) into some solvent is commonly known as solvation process. Thermodynamic functions, such as the free energy, entropy *etc.*, associated with such transfer process are called solvation functions. In the case of aqueous solutions the process is called

as hydration. Thus,

The thermodynamic quantities associated with the transfer of one mole of $M^+ X^-$ (gas) at 1 atm. pressure to the hypothetical unimolal solution are known as the standard state thermodynamic quantities for hydration process.

The basic necessity for understanding the thermodynamics of the solvation process is to know about the standard state free energy of solvation (ΔG_s°) for solute ions (or electrolytes) at different temperatures. The various temperature derivatives of ΔG_s° at constant pressure could subsequently generate the standard entropy (ΔS_s°), enthalpy (ΔH_s°) and heat capacity ($\Delta C_{p(s)}^\circ$) of solvation.

Thus,

$$\Delta S_s^\circ = -[\partial(\Delta G_s^\circ)/\partial T]_P \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta H_s^\circ = [\partial(\Delta G_s^\circ/T)/\partial(1/T)]_P = \Delta G_s^\circ - T[\partial(\Delta G_s^\circ)/\partial T]_P \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta C_{p(s)}^\circ = T[\partial(\Delta S_s^\circ)/\partial T]_P = [\partial(\Delta H_s^\circ)/\partial T]_P \quad (11)$$

The electrical work involved in the transfer of a spherically symmetrical charge from a vacuum to another medium having a dielectric constant, D , is given by the Born charging equation⁶. It will be assumed that such electrical work can be equated to free energy^{4,1}. For an electrolyte consisting of the cations and anions, having ionic solution radii equal to r_c and r_a , respectively, equation (1) becomes

$$\Delta G_T^\circ = \frac{-Ne^2}{2} \left[1 - \frac{1}{D} \right] \left[\frac{n_c Z_c^2}{r_c} + \frac{n_a Z_a^2}{r_a} \right] \quad (12)$$

In general, to avoid the presently arbitrary and non-thermodynamic division of thermodynamic functions into cationic and anionic contributions, the electrolyte form of the equation will be used when possible. The entropy and heat capacity of hydration relationships based on equation (2) become

$$\Delta S_T^\circ = \frac{Ne^2}{2} \frac{1}{D^2} \left(\frac{\partial D}{\partial T} \right)_P \left[\frac{n_c Z_c^2}{r_c} + \frac{n_a Z_a^2}{r_a} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta C_{p_T}^\circ = \frac{Ne^2}{2} \frac{1}{DT} \left[\frac{T^2}{D} \frac{\partial^2 D}{\partial T^2} - \frac{2T^2}{D^2} \left(\frac{\partial D}{\partial T} \right)^2 \right]_P \\ \left[\frac{n_c Z_c^2}{r_c} + \frac{n_a Z_a^2}{r_a} \right] \quad (14)$$

where $Ne^2/2$ has the value $166.027 \text{ \AA cal mol}^{-1}$ and Z is the number of unit charge.

The first approach (Theory no. 1)

The greatest disagreement among various authors on use of the Born free energy equation is on the subject of the effective dielectric constant near an ion. The numerous attempts to modify the Born relationship in this respect will not be repeated here. Instead, the position will be taken that the Born equation is rigorously correct, when

modified by the proper considerations of the hydration process. In our first approach, the first^{4,2} step will be the transfer of an ion gas into some void in the solvent without any disturbance of the solvent. The second step would be to introduce ion-solvent interactions. It is customary to envision some kind of electrostatically induced collapse of the solvent taking place due to the presence of the incorporated solute ion. Our present-day knowledge of electrolytes in water also suggests that such process eventually form a more or less rigid so called primary hydration sheath of water molecules around the ionic species in solution and that the primary hydration sheath of water molecules is perhaps followed by a so called secondary region of water differing from the bulk solvent. For the present, we shall describe such structural hydration effects in terms of an entropy parameter C_s , which represents the entropy loss of water rearranged from the bulk of the solvent into close association with the ions. This entropy term C_s which is designed to as well include statistical entropy terms related to the change of standard state when a gaseous solute ion comes into the solution state. It could also be assumed that C_s is independent of temperature and dependent only upon the electrolyte.

The resulting equations for the thermodynamic properties of hydration of a neutral ensemble of ions become

$$\Delta G_T^\circ = \Delta G_T^\circ + C_s T \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta S_T^\circ = \Delta S_T^\circ - C_s \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta C_{p_T}^\circ = \Delta C_{p_T}^\circ \quad (17)$$

or in more details,

$$\Delta G_T^\circ = -(Ne^2/2RZ) \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) + C_s T \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta H_T^\circ = -(Ne^2/2RZ) \left[1 - \frac{1}{D} - \frac{T}{D^2} \left(\frac{\partial D}{\partial T} \right)_P \right] \quad (19)$$

$$\Delta S_T^\circ = (Ne^2/2RZ) (1/D^2) (\partial D/\partial T)_P - C_s \quad (20)$$

$$\Delta C_{p_T}^\circ = (Ne^2/2RZ) \left[(T/D^2) (\partial^2 D/\partial T^2)_P - (2T/D^2) \left(\frac{\partial D}{\partial T} \right)^2 \right] \quad (21)$$

where,

$$(Ne^2/2RZ) = (Ne^2/2) (n_c Z_c^2/r_c + n_a Z_a^2/r_a) \quad (22)$$

Method of calculation: The constant C_s , can be evaluated from the entropy data at one temperature and the data at other temperatures used to check the validity of the treatment. Calculation of Born hydration functions requires knowledge of the radius parameter ($Ne^2/2RZ$). The parameter could also be evaluated by fitting equations (13) and (16) to the entropy data alone. However, it is useful and will be revealing to define the radius parameter for the electrolyte in terms of a free energy of hydration^{4,2}. From equation (15), we

may have

$$(\text{Ne}^2/2)/R_z = -(\Delta G_f^\circ - C_s T) / \left(1 - \frac{1}{D}\right) \quad (23)$$

The term $(\Delta G_f^\circ - C_s T)$ can be approximated by initially neglecting $-C_s T$, which only amounts to $\sim 5\%$ of the observed free energy of hydration ΔG_f° . Using ΔG_{298}° , the calculated entropy of hydration ΔS_f° can be compared with the experimental value, ΔS_f° , at all temperatures for which data are available and a preliminary value of C_s obtained. This value of $-C_s$ is then used to derive a value of $(\Delta G_f^\circ - C_s T)$ and the whole process repeated until $-C_s$ does not change. In fact, the equation converges rapidly and only one or two trials are required. The standard experimental free energies, ΔG° , at any other temperature can be used as well, but 25° is the most convenient. When the values of C_s and the radius parameter of any electrolytic water systems have been known the corresponding various thermodynamic functions can be calculated from equations (18) to (21).

Results and discussion: Since the free energy of hydration changes only 5-10% for most electrolytes over the temperature range under discussion ($0-300^\circ$), a more sensitive test of present theory can be obtained by examination of the differences in hydration energy between two temperatures,

Experimentally, this difference in the free energy of hydration can be obtained from the free energy functions,

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta G_{T_2}^\circ - \Delta G_{T_1}^\circ) = & \left(\frac{\bar{G}_{T_2}^\circ - \bar{H}_{298}^\circ}{T_2} \right)_{\text{aq}} T_2 \\ & + \sum_{\text{gases}} \left(\frac{G_{T_1}^\circ - H_{298}^\circ}{T_1} \right) T_1 - \left(\frac{\bar{G}_{T_1}^\circ - \bar{H}_{298}^\circ}{T_1} \right)_{\text{aq}} T_1 \\ & - \sum_{\text{gases}} \left(\frac{G_{T_2}^\circ - H_{298}^\circ}{T_2} \right) T_2 \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

From equations (12), (15) and (18), it follows that

$$\Delta G_{T_2}^\circ - \Delta G_{T_1}^\circ = (\Delta G_{T_2}^B - G_{T_1}^B) + C_s(T_2 - T_1) \quad (26)$$

where,

$$(\Delta G_{T_2}^B - \Delta G_{T_1}^B) = - \left(\frac{1}{D_2} - \frac{1}{D_1} \right) \left[\frac{(\Delta G_f^\circ - C_s T)}{(1 - 1/D)} \right] \quad (27)$$

Figs. 1 and 2 illustrate such a test of the basic free energy relationship. T_1 is set at 25° . These relationships predict that the difference between the observed free energy differences and the Born energy differences (equation 26) should be a linear function of T , with a slope of C_s . The agreement between theory and experiment illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2 is essentially perfect to within the average

Fig. 1. Free energy diagram showing the differences between observed and Born energies of hydration at 25° and t° (kcal mol^{-1}), straight lines predicted from Theory no. 1 and points calculated from experimental data.

Fig. 2. Free energy diagram showing the differences between observed and Born energies of hydration at 25° and t° (kcal mol^{-1}); straight lines predicted from Theory no. 1 and points calculated from the experimental data.

experimental error of a few tens of calories. In this test, the values of C_S were the same as those evaluated from the entropy data.

One of the basic assumptions in the present treatment is that the radius parameter $(Ne^2/2)/R_Z$ in equation (22) is temperature independent. In Table I the values of $1/R_Z$ has been calculated for some electrolytes, both to test this assumption and to note the size of the ions involved. Although we have deliberately refrained from considering

TABLE I—TEMPERATURE TEST OF THE RADIUS FUNCTION $(1/R_Z), \text{\AA}^{-1}$

Temp. °C	NaCl	BaCl ₂	HCl	HBr	GdCl ₃	CaI
0	1.111 7	2.811 5	2.092 8	—	6.638 9	0.820 6
25	1.112 0	2.813 7	2.092 7	2.025 6	6.638 95	0.821 2
50	1.112 1	2.814 0	2.092 6	2.025 5	6.639 6	0.821 3
75	1.112 1	2.813 9	2.092 5	2.025 2	6.639 3	0.821 2
100	1.112 1	2.813 5	2.092 5	2.025 2	6.639 9	0.821 0
150	1.111 9	2.813 9	2.092 6	2.025 7		
200	1.111 6	2.813 5	2.093 5	2.026 7		
250	1.112 0					
300	1.114 4					

individual ions in the basic derivations fixing up of the radius of any particular ion will enable one to compare the ionic radii of many cations and anions in solution. The known experimental values of ΔG° at 25°, was obtained by the relationship,

$$\Delta G_T^\circ = \left[\frac{G^\circ - H_{298}^\circ}{T} \right]_{aq} - \sum \left[\frac{G^\circ - H_{298}^\circ}{T} \right]_T + \Delta H_{298}^\circ \quad (28)$$

where, ΔH_{298}° is the hydration enthalpy. Table I obviously demonstrates that the radius parameter is temperature independent.

In Figs. 3 and 4, the calculated values of the entropy of hydration (ΔS_h°) of a number of electrolytes have been plotted with the corresponding known experimental values at different temperatures. The ability of the model to quantitatively predict the entropy and its temperature variation over so large a range of temperature with only one arbitrary constant leads strong support to the validity of this use of the Born equation.

Differentiating equation (15) one would obtain,

$$[\delta(\Delta S)/\delta T]_P = [\delta(\Delta S^B)/\delta T]_P \quad (29)$$

Since, $[\delta(\Delta S)/\delta T]_P = \Delta C_p/T$, it follows that

$$\Delta C_p = \Delta C_p^B \quad (30)$$

that is, the entropy constant, C_S , cancels out in consideration of the heat capacities, except for a small effect in determination of the radius parameter. However, the errors in the various derivatives of the dielectric constant data, as well as in the experimental heat capacities themselves, make it unnecessary to be so precise in our evaluation of

Fig. 3. Comparison of observed (symbols) and predicted (shaded band) entropy of hydration ($\Delta S_h^\circ, \text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) (Theory no. 1), width of the band was fixed from the uncertainties in dielectric constant data.

Fig. 4. Comparison of observed (symbols) and predicted (shaded band) entropy of hydration ($\Delta S_h^\circ, \text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) (Theory no. 1). The width of the band was fixed from the uncertainties in dielectric constant data.

$(Ne^2/2)R_2$. Consequently, to a very good approximation,

$$\Delta C_p^B = \frac{1}{DT} \left[\frac{T^2}{D} \left(\frac{\delta^2 D}{\delta T^2} \right)_P - \frac{2T^2}{D^2} \left(\frac{\delta D}{\delta T} \right)^2 \right] \left[\frac{\Delta G_{298}^0}{1-1/D} \right] \quad (31)$$

is obtained from equations (14) and (22) and involves no arbitrary constants. In Figs. 5 and 6

Fig. 5. Predicated (band) and observed (symbols) heat capacities of hydration ($\Delta C_p^0(h)$, cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) (Theory no. 1).

Fig. 6. Predicated (band) and observed (symbols) heat capacities of hydration ($\Delta C_p^0(h)$, cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) (Theory no. 1).

the experimental heat capacities of hydration and a band of values predicated from equation (31) have been plotted for NaCl(aq) and BaCl₂(aq). The agreement is good above 75° or so.

Since one of the advantages of the proposed treatment lies in the accuracy of the predicted thermodynamic functions, it is necessary to define clearly the adopted values of D which are being used. Table 2 lists the values of D and its first and second temperature derivatives at different temperatures used in the calculations. In Table 3, the values of $1/R_2$ and C_s for different electrolytes which may be used in the various thermodynamic predictions for aqueous electrolytes at different temperatures have been listed.

TABLE 2—SMOOTHED DIELECTRIC CONSTANT DATA FOR WATER^a

Temp. °C	D	-(dD/dT) ^o	(d ² D/dT ²) ^d
0	87.74 ^a	0.400 1	0.001 88
25	78.904 ^a	0.356 0	0.001 64
50	69.91 ^a	0.318 5	0.001 45
75	62.43 ^a	0.285 5	0.001 29
100	55.72 ^a	0.254 6	0.001 19
125	49.35 ^b	0.214 5	0.000 98
150	43.89 ^b	0.205 5	0.000 84
175	39.02 ^b	0.186 6	0.000 70
200	34.59 ^b	0.169 2	0.000 57
225	30.50 ^b	0.156 9	0.000 43
250	26.71 ^b	0.147 1	0.000 29
275	23.11 ^b	0.141 0	0.000 15
300	19.66 ^b	0.139 0	0.000 02
325	16.21 ^b	0.140 5	-0.000 11
350	12.60 ^b	0.143 7	-0.000 21
370	9.74 ^b	0.148 0	-0.000 28

^aRef. 44. The values : ^a±0.05, ^b±0.01, ^o±0.0120, ^d±0.00020.

TABLE 3—RADIUS FUNCTION ($1/R_2$) AND ENTROPY PARAMETERS (C_s) FOR DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES

Electrolytes	$1/R_2$ Å ⁻¹	C_s cal mol ⁻¹
HCl	2.029 8	29.4
LiCl	1.996 6	44.3
NaCl	1.112 1	34.2
KCl	0.992 7	26.6
RbCl	0.954 3	24.8
CsCl	0.909 2	24.6
AgCl	0.174 5	33.3
TlCl	1.001 2	26.5
InCl	1.017 8	27.9
CuCl	1.615 4	32.9
BeCl ₂	4.669 9	90.1
MgCl ₂	3.800 5	68.0
CaCl ₂	3.322 1	65.4
BaCl ₂	2.813 7	61.3
TiCl ₂	3.709 0	72.7
VCl ₂	3.805 9	74.3
CrCl ₂	3.790 2	72.7
MnCl ₂	3.708 9	68.6
FeCl ₂	3.851 3	82.3
CoCl ₂	3.925 6	75.5
CuCl ₂	4.062 8	69.8
ZnCl ₂	3.980 6	66.2
HgCl ₂	3.681 6	60.3

(Table 3 contd.)

CdCl ₂	3.651 8	67.9
SbCl ₃	3.292 3	62.4
PbCl ₂	3.193 4	57.8
RuCl ₃	4.003 6	67.3
PdCl ₂	3.935 1	77.7
AlCl ₃	8.280 5	90.5
YCl ₃	6.734 6	103.0
LaCl ₃	6.937 3	99.6
TiCl ₄	7.593 8	105.8
VCl ₄	7.844 8	106.9
CrCl ₃	8.151 0	96.5
MnCl ₂	8.119 0	100.0
FeCl ₃	7.918 1	99.9
CoCl ₂	8.247 1	100.0
NiCl ₂		
BiCl ₃	6.743 3	86.0
GaCl ₃	6.071 3	152.9
InCl ₃	7.474 7	68.8
TlCl ₃	7.797 2	78.4
GdCl ₃	6.639 5	101.8
MoCl ₅	7.694 8	102.6
RuCl ₂	7.865 1	101.0
SnCl ₄	13.029 0	112.6

The second approach (Theory no. 2) :

In an recent work, it has been found that the overall interaction phenomenon in electrolyte-solvent system can be conveniently split into two additive parts, (i) the interaction due to the presence of an ionic species of finite size into a uniform dielectric solvent system, and (ii) the so called specific interactions occurring at various distances apart from the incorporated ion which may result in the formation of the so called multi-layer solvation zones around the solute ion⁴⁶. The free energy involved in the first part of the interaction process as mentioned above may be conveniently estimated with the help of Born charging equation⁶. A prior fixation of the value of the interaction free energy for the second part (denoted as ΔG^*), on the other hand, seems to be difficult and may require various kinds of speculation. It has been, however, realised that ΔG^* which apparently has its major contribution in the strong interactions in the vicinity of a dissolved ion would be relatively insensitive to temperature variations⁴⁷. Consequently, some interesting possibilities arise for accurate theoretical predictions of the related thermodynamic properties of the system at different temperatures⁴⁶⁻⁵⁰.

According to the above theory⁵⁰ proposed on the basis of the scaled particle approach⁵¹ which has been extremely successful in thermodynamic predictions for solvation processes with neutral gases as solutes, the solvation process of electrolytes (or ions) can be seen as the simple combination of two steps, (i) the formation of a cavity of appropriate size in the solvent system for the accommodation of the solute species, and (ii) the introduction of the solute ion into the cavity which interacts with the surrounding solvent. Consequently, when this interaction process is again subdivided as stated

above into the (i) Born-type electrostatic interaction and (ii) the sum of the other various kind of specific interactions occurring in the various regions around the incorporated solute ions, which the Born continuum model cannot recognise, the standard free energy of solvation, ΔG_s^0 , for electrolytes can be represented as,

$$\Delta G_s^0 = \Delta G^C + \Delta G^I + \Delta G_X \quad (32)$$

$$\Delta G_s^0 = \Delta G^C + (\Delta G^B + \Delta G^*) + \Delta G_X \quad (33)$$

where, ΔG^C , ΔG^I , ΔG^B , ΔG^* and ΔG_X are the Gibbs free energy of cavity formation, of all interactions, of Born type electrostatic interactions, of specific interactions which the Born equation cannot recognise, and the free energy change due to the standard state conversion, respectively. The various temperature derivatives of equation (33) eliminates the unknown term ΔG^* which is assumed to be temperature independent (*i.e.* $[\delta(\Delta G^*)/\delta T]_P=0$), and gives equations for entropy, enthalpy and heat capacity of hydration. Thus,

$$\Delta S_s^0 = \Delta S^C + \Delta S^B + \Delta S_X \quad (34)$$

$$\Delta C_{p_s}^0 = \Delta C_p^C + \Delta C_p^B + \Delta C_{p_X} \quad (35)$$

It can be easily seen that every term in the right sides of the above two equations are defined and can be calculated without difficulty, as described below.

Method of calculations : In order to use equations (32) to (35) for thermodynamic prediction, one must know how to calculate the thermodynamic functions for cavity formation. A number of ways including the one which involves the scaled particle theory (SPT) may be available for the estimation of the work associated with cavity formation and its temperature derivatives. The use of SPT is generally believed to lead to the most accurate values⁵⁰. Moreover, the method can be easily simplified by assuming both the solute species and the solvent molecules to be incompressible hard spheres⁵¹. This simplification, however, hardly affects the accuracy in the results, particularly in the case of ion species as the solute as in the present case where the interaction energy in the transfer process predominates. Followings are the expressions for various thermodynamic functions for cavity formation⁵¹,

$$\Delta G^C = K_0 + K_1 d_{12} + K_2 d_{12}^2 + K_3 d_{12}^3 \quad (36)$$

$$\Delta H^C = B_0 + B_1 d_{12} + B_2 d_{12}^2 + B_3 d_{12}^3 \quad (37)$$

$$\Delta S^C = (\Delta H^C - \Delta G^C)/T \quad (38)$$

$$\Delta C_p^C = C_H \Delta H^C - (C_0 + C_1 d_{12} + C_2 d_{12}^2 + C_3 d_{12}^3) \quad (39)$$

The values of K, B and C coefficients can be obtained using standard equations⁵¹. The values of these coefficients for various solvents at different temperatures and the corresponding solvent diameter (d_1) have been calculated and listed elsewhere^{46-48, 52}. Twice Pauling's crystal radius values⁵³ have been used for d_2 and $d_{12} = (d_1 + d_2)/2$

i.e. the sum of the radii of both the solute species and the solvent molecule.

After having calculated the various cavity functions one has to calculate the thermodynamics of interaction as depicted in equations (33) to (35). For the calculation of the Born interaction function in this approach, one need not modify the Born equation by fixing the radius parameter but can use the original equation with crystal radius of the ionic solute and the bulk dielectric constant. The thermodynamic functions for the change of standard state from one atmosphere gas to hypothetical unimolal solution can be calculated by the following equations,

$$\Delta G_x = RT \ln(RTM_1/1000 V_1) \quad (40)$$

$$\Delta S_x = \alpha_p RT - R - R \ln(RTM_1/1000V_1) \quad (41)$$

$$\Delta C_{p(x)} = 2\alpha_p RT - R + RT^2(\delta\alpha_p/\delta T)_P \quad (42)$$

where, M_1 , V_1 and α_p are the molecular weight, molal volume and coefficient of cubical thermal expansion of the solvent, respectively.

In equation (33), all terms except the specific interaction free energy ΔG^* can be calculated and with the help of the corresponding known experimental free energy of hydration the values ΔG^* at different temperature can be easily generated.

It may be noted that like the earlier approach the ionic solute radius has been assumed to be temperature-independent. The crystal radius value was used both for the SPT equations for cavity and the Born equation for electrostatic interaction thermodynamic functions.

Results and discussion : The values of ΔG^* for some typical 1 : 1, 2 : 1, 3 : 1 electrolytes obtained from equation (33) at different temperatures have been listed in Table 4. It may be evident from Table 4 that the value of ΔG^* is fairly constant upto around 100° or so. Above that temperature, there may be a slight tendency that the value would increase with temperature. Considering the much greater uncertainties in the available experimental values of free energy of hydration at higher temperatures, this small magnitude of the apparent increment in the values of ΔG^* at high temperatures would for the time being be ignored.

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE TEST FOR THE SPECIFIC INTERACTION FREE ENERGY TERM, ΔG^* (kcal mol⁻¹)

Temp. °C	NaCl	BaCl ₂	GdCl ₃	CsI
0	81.2	206.9	697.4	30.4
25	80.8	206.0	696.6	29.2
50	80.8	205.9	696.4	28.6
75	81.0	206.2	696.7	28.4
100	81.2	206.8	697.1	28.3
125	81.5	207.2		
150	82.2	208.3		
175	82.7	209.3		
200	83.4	210.4		
225	84.2			
250	85.0			
275	85.9			
300	86.6			

In Figs. 7, 8 and 11, the calculated values of ΔG^c , ΔS^c and ΔC_p^c have been plotted against temperature. Figs. 9 and 10 show the comparison between the calculated and the experimental values of ΔS^c for different electrolytes at different temperatures. It is evident that as in the case of prediction by Theory no. 1 (Figs. 3 and 4), the agreement is good throughout the temperature range. The comparison of the predicted values of ΔC_p^c for hydration with those of the experimental values^{4,5} can be seen in Figs. 12 and 13. A comparison between predicted and observed entropy of hydration of a number of other salts may be seen elsewhere.

Comparative assessment of the two theories :

One of the main objectives of the present work is to construct a theory of electrolyte solution which will be able to predict with sufficient accuracy the thermodynamic behaviours of electrolytes and ions in solution at all temperatures. Presently, though useful thermodynamic data for various electrolytes at room temperature may be available, the corresponding data at elevated temperatures are not easily available. The necessary compilation obviously has not been done. Considering the fact that so much time has been spent to obtain thermodynamic data of various electrolytes in solution at room temperature alone one could easily see the enormous volume of experimental work necessary for collecting such thermodynamic data at various

Fig. 7. Variation of ΔG^c , (kcal mol⁻¹) with temperature.

Fig. 8 Variation of ΔS° ($\text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) with temperature.

Fig. 10. Predicted (band) and observed (symbols) entropies of hydration ΔS_h° , $\text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$ (Theory no. 2).

Fig. 9. Predicted (band) and observed (symbols) entropies of hydration ΔS_h° , $\text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$ (Theory no. 2).

Fig. 11. Variation of ΔC_p° ($\text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) with temperature.

elevated temperatures. Perhaps only an appropriate theory can provide some relief in lessening the burden of immediate experimental works one would need in this regard.

The success of the above two theories in predicting the entropy, heat capacity and also the free

Fig. 12. Predicted (band) and observed (symbols) heat capacities of hydration, $\Delta C_{p(h)}^0$, cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ (Theory no. 2).

Fig. 13. Predicted (band) and observed (symbols) heat capacities of hydration, $\Delta C_{p(h)}^0$, cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ (Theory no. 2).

energy of transfer from one temperature to another could provide the answer to this long felt prime need of a short cut procedure to obtain thermodynamic data for electrolytes in solution at elevated temperatures without going through the lengthy and different experiments.

In Theory no. 1, we have to know the experimental free energy of hydration at least at one temperature for fixing the effective temperature independent solution radii of ions and subsequently to determine the entropy parameter C_s which is again insensitive to temperature change. These terms will be needed for the theoretical predictions of thermodynamic data for electrolytes. The value of C_s will be different for different electrolyte though it is not adjustable as such. Because of this dependence on the experimental hydration energy, the theory itself cannot provide any thermodynamic means for splitting the cationic and the anionic contributions from the thermodynamic data of the neutral electrolyte. On the otherhand, Theory no. 2 is capable of accurately predicting hydration entropy and heat capacity of electrolytes in solution at different temperatures without using any arbitrary parameters of taking help of any experimental thermodynamic data. It also gives accurate predictions for temperature effect on the free energy of hydration. The absolute value of the free energy of hydration of electrolyte at different temperatures, however, can be predicted only with the help of experimental free energy of hydration at one temperature^{4,5}. Because of this unique feature of complete independence from experimental thermodynamic data as well as arbitrary parameters, Theory no. 2 provides us with the unique opportunity to have the theoretical means to identify the ionic hydration data at various temperatures without taking recourse to any non-thermodynamic assumptions^{4,8}.

The only method available until recently for fixing the ionic scale of the entropy of hydration at different temperatures is due to Criss and Cobble^{5,4}. The method of the choice has been purely arbitrary and the authors themselves recognised their arbitrary assignments are not necessarily unique and there is a probability the entropies of ions will have absolute values different from those assigned by them at elevated temperatures^{5,5}. The agreement in the values of the ionic entropies assigned by the arbitrary method of Criss and Cobble^{5,4} and the predicted values by our approach (Theory no. 2) around 25° is, however good. But as we go to higher temperatures around 100° or more the disagreement is almost total (Fig. 14). We, however, recommend our predicted values for ionic hydration entropies at higher temperatures from various considerations^{4,8}. It may be noted that the experimental values of hydration entropies of the neutral ensemble of the cations and anions agree very well with the corresponding predicted values. Therefore, the problem may be with the arbitrary method of dividing the electrolyte thermodynamic

Fig. 14. Temperature behaviours of the entropy of hydration (ΔS_h^0 , cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) of a few typical ions. Continuous lines represent this work and broken line represent Ref. 54

values to the corresponding cationic and anionic contributions. Table 5 contains the predicted hydration entropy values for various ions at different temperatures. The effect of surfaces dipole potential⁵⁶ in the process of ionic transfer from vacuum to the solvent is negligible particularly at higher temperatures and hence has not been considered⁴⁸.

Prediction of the ionic hydration entropy involves the ionic crystal radius. In the data presented in Table 5, Pauling's crystal radius values⁵⁸ have been used. It may be noted here that sometimes the experimental crystal radius values of Gourary and Adrian⁵⁷ gives better results in some of the predictions. However, experimental radius values are available only for limited number of ions and hence the Pauling's radius values have been used for our calculations. The values of the radius for the multi-atom ions were in many cases taken from the compilation by Millero⁵⁸.

Cu ⁺	0.96	23.8	23.4	23.7	24.2	25.0
Ag ⁺	1.26	24.1	23.4	23.0	22.7	22.7
Au ⁺	1.37	24.7	23.8	23.1	22.6	22.4
Ga ⁺	1.13	23.5	23.2	23.1	23.1	23.5
In ⁺	1.32	24.4	23.6	23.0	22.6	22.5
Tl ⁺	1.40	24.9	23.9	23.2	22.6	22.3
F ⁻	1.36	24.7	23.7	23.1	22.7	22.5
Cl ⁻	1.81	28.8	26.6	24.9	23.3	22.1
Br ⁻	1.95	30.8	27.9	25.8	23.9	22.3
I ⁻	2.16	33.3	30.2	27.4	25.0	22.9
OH ⁻	1.38	24.8	22.8	23.1	22.6	22.3
CN ⁻	1.92	30.1	27.6	25.6	23.7	22.2
NO ₂ ⁻	2.03	31.5	28.7	26.4	24.2	22.5
SCN ⁻	2.27	35.0	29.2	26.4	25.6	23.9
CIO ₄ ⁻	2.29	35.5	29.4	26.6	25.7	23.3
BPh ₄ ⁻	4.62	91.0	76.6	63.6	51.8	41.2
NH ₄ ⁺	1.48	25.5	24.9	23.4	22.6	22.2
HMo ₆ ⁺	3.47	58.8	50.5	43.1	36.3	30.3
NEt ₄ ⁺	4.00	72.6	61.6	51.9	42.9	34.9
NPr ₄ ⁺	4.52	87.9	74.0	61.6	51.1	40.1
NBu ₄ ⁺	4.94	101.6	85.1	70.4	56.9	44.8
NPen ₄ ⁺	5.80	114.8	95.4	78.5	63.0	49.2
NHEx ₄ ⁺	5.65	127.4	106.0	86.9	69.4	53.8
NHep ₄ ⁺	5.92	138.1	114.7	93.8	74.6	57.5
AsPh ₄ ⁺	4.70	93.6	78.7	65.3	53.0	42.1
Be ²⁺	0.31	121.4	134.1	148.5	164.9	184.7
Mg ²⁺	0.65	65.0	70.7	77.2	84.6	93.6
Ca ²⁺	0.99	49.4	52.5	56.2	60.5	65.9
Sr ²⁺	1.13	46.4	48.8	51.7	55.1	59.6
Ba ²⁺	1.35	43.7	45.1	47.0	49.4	52.7
Od ²⁺	0.97	49.9	53.2	56.3	61.4	67.0
Mn ²⁺	0.80	56.1	60.5	65.5	71.2	78.4
Pb ²⁺	1.20	45.3	47.3	49.9	53.0	57.1
Hg ²⁺	1.10	44.3	49.4	52.5	56.2	60.8
Cu ²⁺	0.74	59.2	64.0	69.5	75.9	83.7
Fe ²⁺	0.76	58.1	62.8	68.1	74.3	81.8
Zn ²⁺	0.74	59.2	64.0	69.5	75.9	83.7
Co ²⁺	0.74	59.2	64.0	69.5	75.9	83.7
Ni ²⁺	0.72	60.3	65.3	71.0	77.6	85.7
Sn ²⁺	1.12	46.6	49.0	51.9	55.5	60.0
Cr ²⁺	0.84	54.4	58.4	63.1	68.5	75.3
Pd ²⁺	0.86	53.6	57.5	62.0	67.3	73.8
Ra ²⁺	1.40	43.3	44.5	46.2	48.4	51.4
Ge ²⁺	0.93	51.1	54.6	58.6	63.4	69.3
Ti ²⁺	0.90	52.1	55.8	60.0	65.0	71.1
S ²⁻	1.84	43.1	42.6	42.6	43.0	44.3
Al ³⁺	0.50	166.3	184.0	204.0	226.9	254.4
Fe ³⁺	0.64	132.9	146.8	162.4	180.2	201.7
Cr ³⁺	0.69	124.7	137.3	151.5	167.8	187.1
Mn ³⁺	0.66	129.6	142.8	157.7	174.8	195.5
Co ³⁺	0.63	135.0	148.9	164.5	182.5	204.2
Ni ³⁺	0.62	137.0	151.1	167.0	185.3	207.3
Co ³⁺	1.11	85.6	92.6	100.7	108.5	121.7
Ga ³⁺	0.62	137.0	151.1	167.0	185.3	207.3
In ³⁺	0.81	108.9	119.4	131.8	144.9	161.5
Tl ³⁺	0.95	95.9	104.5	114.4	125.8	139.7
Sc ³⁺	0.81	108.9	119.4	131.3	144.9	161.5
Y ³⁺	0.93	97.5	106.4	116.5	128.2	142.4
Gd ³⁺	1.02	90.9	98.8	107.8	118.3	131.1
La ³⁺	1.15	83.5	90.2	97.9	107.3	118.0
Th ³⁺	1.14	84.0	90.8	98.6	107.7	118.9
U ³⁺	1.11	85.6	92.6	100.7	108.5	121.7
Np ³⁺	1.09	86.7	93.9	102.2	111.8	123.7
Cr ⁴⁺	0.56	257.8	286.1	317.9	355.0	398.4
Mn ⁴⁺	0.54	266.8	296.2	329.2	367.1	412.7
Ti ⁴⁺	0.68	215.1	238.2	264.2	294.1	330.1
Ge ⁴⁺	0.53	271.6	301.6	335.2	373.8	420.3
Zr ⁴⁺	0.80	185.5	204.9	226.8	252.0	282.4
Sn ⁴⁺	0.71	206.7	228.8	253.7	282.2	316.7
Co ⁴⁺	1.01	151.4	166.3	183.3	202.8	223.6
Pb ⁴⁺	0.84	177.6	196.0	216.8	240.7	269.6
U ⁴⁺	0.97	156.7	172.3	190.1	210.5	236.3
Np ⁴⁺	0.95	159.5	175.5	193.7	214.6	240.0
V ⁵⁺	0.59	377.1	419.2	466.6	520.9	586.2
As ⁵⁺	0.47	469.7	522.8	582.5	650.9	733.1

TABLE 5—PREDICTED VALUES OF STANDARD ENTROPY OF HYDRATION OF IONS (ΔS_h^0) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE (°C)

Ions	r_c	ΔS_h^0 , cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹				
		0°	25°	50°	75°	100°
H ⁺	—	3.8	4.5	5.1	5.8	7.3
Li ⁺	0.60	26.1	27.2	28.8	30.5	32.6
Na ⁺	0.95	23.4	23.5	23.9	24.4	25.2
K ⁺	1.33	24.5	23.6	23.1	22.7	22.6
Rb ⁺	1.48	25.5	24.3	23.4	22.6	22.2
Cs ⁺	1.69	27.5	25.7	24.2	23.0	22.0

(Table 5 contd.)

Pd ²⁺	0.86	165.1	208.5	281.9	415.7	695.5	1 186.1
Ra ²⁺	1.40	103.0	129.1	173.6	266.5	425.9	721.4
Ge ²⁺	0.93	153.0	193.1	260.8	384.6	642.9	1 095.4
Ti ²⁺	0.90	158.0	199.4	269.4	397.4	664.4	1 132.6
S ²⁻	1.84	78.0	98.0	131.6	195.8	328.2	544.5
Al ³⁺	0.50	621.1	792.1	1 079.3	1 600.8	2 701.4	4 648.5
Fe ³⁺	0.64	486.6	619.9	844.1	1 251.2	2 109.8	3 628.7
Cr ³⁺	0.69	451.7	575.3	783.2	1 160.8	1 956.6	3 359.7
Mn ³⁺	0.66	472.0	601.3	818.6	1 213.4	2 045.7	3 513.3
Co ³⁺	0.63	494.2	629.7	857.4	1 271.0	2 143.3	3 631.5
Ni ³⁺	0.62	502.1	638.5	862.5	1 291.5	2 177.9	3 741.1
Ce ³⁺	1.11	282.8	359.0	487.8	722.6	1 215.0	2 081.5
Ga ³⁺	0.62	502.1	638.5	862.5	1 291.5	2 177.9	3 741.1
In ³⁺	0.81	385.7	490.7	667.6	989.2	1 666.2	2 859.2
Tl ³⁺	0.95	329.6	419.3	569.6	843.8	1 420.2	2 485.1
Sc ³⁺	0.81	385.7	490.7	667.6	989.2	1 666.2	2 859.2
Y ³⁺	0.93	336.6	427.9	581.3	861.9	1 450.8	2 487.9
Gd ³⁺	1.02	307.3	390.5	530.7	785.8	1 322.5	2 266.8
La ³⁺	1.15	273.1	346.6	470.9	697.6	1 172.6	2 008.4
Th ³⁺	1.14	275.4	349.7	475.0	703.7	1 182.9	2 026.2
U ³⁺	1.11	282.8	359.0	487.8	722.6	1 215.0	2 081.5
Np ³⁺	1.09	287.9	365.6	496.7	735.8	1 237.3	2 120.0
Cr ⁴⁺	0.56	981.9	1 253.8	1 710.4	2 539.2	4 290.0	7 381.5
Mn ⁴⁺	0.54	1 018.1	1 300.0	1 773.6	2 633.2	4 449.0	7 655.6
Ti ⁴⁺	0.68	809.7	1 033.4	1 409.2	2 091.6	3 532.4	6 075.6
Ge ⁴⁺	0.53	1 037.2	1 324.5	1 807.0	2 682.8	4 533.1	7 800.4
Zr ⁴⁺	0.80	689.1	879.0	1 196.00	1 778.3	3 002.0	5 161.5
Sn ⁴⁺	0.71	775.7	898.9	1 349.8	2 003.4	3 383.0	5 818.1
Ce ⁴⁺	1.01	546.9	697.0	949.7	1 409.2	2 377.1	4 084.4
Pb ⁴⁺	0.84	656.5	837.4	1 141.4	1 693.8	2 858.8	4 914.8
U ⁴⁺	0.97	569.2	725.6	990.0	1 467.1	2 475.3	4 253.6
Np ⁴⁺	0.95	581.1	740.9	1 009.5	1 498.0	2 527.5	4 343.6
V ⁵⁺	0.59	1 453.0	1 856.6	2 534.4	3 764.5	6 364.0	10 956.1
As ⁵⁺	0.47	1 822.4	2 329.3	3 180.4	4 724.9	7 989.7	13 758.1
Sb ⁵⁺	0.62	1 383.0	1 767.0	2 411.9	3 582.4	6 055.9	10 425.1
Br ⁵⁺	0.74	1 159.7	1 481.2	2 021.4	3 002.0	5 073.3	8 731.5
Nb ⁵⁺	0.70	1 225.6	1 565.6	2 136.7	3 173.3	5 361.4	9 231.5
Cr ⁶⁺	0.52	2 369.9	3 029.9	4 138.0	6 148.8	10 399.9	17 912.4
Mo ⁶⁺	0.62	1 988.6	2 542.0	3 471.2	5 157.5	8 722.0	15 020.3
Mn ⁷⁺	0.46	3 642.8	4 658.9	6 364.3	9 459.2	16 003.7	27 570.8

Fig 15. Correspondence diagram illustrating the linear relationship between the predicted entropies of hydration of ions (ΔS_h^0 , cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) at 100° and at other temperatures.

Criss and Cobble⁵⁴ observed that ionic entropies at higher temperatures are linearly related to ionic entropies at other temperatures and proposed their correspondence relationship,

$$S_{i_2} = a + b S_{i_1} \quad \dots (43)$$

where, S_{i_2} and S_{i_1} are the entropies at temperatures t_2 and t_1 , respectively, and a and b are the coefficients of the linear equation and are constant for a particular pair of temperatures. They however obtained the ionic entropies from the experimental partial molal entropy data of the corresponding salt consisting of the particular cations and anions. Some arbitrary means were used for the division into the ionic parts and it was assumed that the cations and anions will follow a separate linear relationship to produce different correspondence curves for cations and anions^{54, 55}. We have shown that if one could fix the ionic scale of entropy properly the cations and anions will have the same correspondence curves⁴⁸. It is also possible to plot the entropy of hydration of ions to a linear correspondence curve. Fig. 15 shows a few typical correspondence plots with entropy of hydration. The entropy of hydration values at 100° were taken

as reference temperature values. The values of the coefficients a (intercept) and b (slope) for each temperature plots with 100° as the reference temperature have been listed in Table 6.

TABLE 6—CORRESPONDENCE CONSTANTS a (in cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) AND b FOR THE CALCULATED ENTROPY OF HYDRATION (ΔS_h^0) OF IONS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

Temp. °C	a	b
0	-14.76	0.529
25	-10.92	0.599
50	-7.37	0.741
75	-3.75	0.861
100*	0.00	1.000
125	8.88	1.161
150	8.27	1.351
175	12.58	1.668
200	17.62	1.922
225	23.84	2.178
250	32.01	2.666
275	43.71	3.410
300	62.23	4.655
325	92.37	6.867
350	164.87	11.640
370	296.17	20.056

* Reference tem. (see equation 43).

The theory should also provide proper guidance for fixing the ionic scale for heat capacity of hydration at different temperatures. But the large limits of uncertainties of the second temperature derivatives of the solvent dielectric constant particularly at higher temperatures have been proved to be a serious handle to the accurate heat capacity predictions (Figs. 5, 6 and 12, 13). Detail discussion about heat capacity predictions by different theories will appear elsewhere^{5,2}.

Conclusion :

From the two simple but highly successful approaches described in the present communication, it may be concluded that in spite of the various criticisms put forward from time to time^{3,5,9} against its use for thermodynamic predictions, the Born equation⁶ even in its original primitive form can provide us the basis of a theory of electrolytic solution which can accurately predict the various thermodynamic behaviours of ions and electrolytes in solution at all temperatures. Moreover, the use of the primitive Born model makes the mathematical calculations for prediction strikingly simple. This remarkable success of the Born equation perhaps indicates that particularly at some higher temperature and thereafter the thermodynamic behaviours of ions in solution is directed mainly by the electrostatic field effect and the so called structural effect is only significant at some lower temperatures where the solvent hydrogen bonding is sufficiently strong. The same observation has been varified recently, by experiments with high temperature aqueous electrolyte solutions^{4,6}. Yet another advantage of the present approaches is that they can be universally applied to non-aqueous and mixed-solvent systems^{4,7}.

Further works in this line which may reveal the possible constituents of temperature insensitive quantities C_p and ΔG^* or their slight variations at extreme temperatures and also their relationship with the so called solvation numbers would be no doubt interesting.

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